

A Study of Teaching Aptitude on D.El.Ed. Performance and CTET Success: A Correlation Analysis

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Abstract

This study examines the relationship between the performance of pupil-teachers enrolled in the Diploma in Elementary Education (D.El.Ed.) program and their teaching aptitude, with respect to their result in the Central Teacher Eligibility Test (CTET). It aims to identify the correlation between the academic performance in D.El.Ed and result in CTET. The study also takes in account the academic discipline viz Science, Commerce, Humanities of D.El.Ed trainees and their gender as well to observe the influence of these factors on the teaching aptitude of trainees on teaching aptitude and exam performance. Data was collected using multiple sources, including the Teaching Aptitude Scale, school performance records (10th and 12th grades), and D.El.Ed. academic performance, alongside CTET results. This comparative research helps in explaining the factors that influence pupil-teachers' success in their professional training and in exams like the CTET, contributing to the broader understanding of teacher effectiveness and preparation

Aptitude is one of the important factors that determine the behaviour of an individual. There is no information about the Teaching Aptitude of the candidates pursuing D.El.Ed. Therefore, there is an urgent need to collect information about the teaching aptitude of the pupil teachers pursuing D.El.Ed. in order to strategize the interventions required in making a good teacher. Further, it will also be beneficial to understand the performance of pupil teachers in D.El.Ed in relation to their teaching aptitude and school performance in order to improve the quality of the Teacher Education programme.

Key word: Pupil Teachers, Teaching Aptitude, CTET, School Performance, D.El.Ed.

INTRODUCTION

Teaching aptitude is the inherent ability, skills, and disposition that enable an individual to effectively facilitate learning, transact curriculum and manage classroom dynamics. In the context of Diploma in Elementary Education (D.El.Ed.) programs, which prepare future educators for elementary teaching, understanding the relationship between teaching aptitude and academic outcomes is crucial. This relationship not only influences the effectiveness of future teachers but also impacts the quality of education delivered to young learners. This relationship goes a long way in determining the effectiveness of teaching aptitude of trainees. In programs like the Diploma in Elementary Education (D.El.Ed.), the emphasis often lies on the methodologies of teaching, lesson planning and classroom management. However, exploring the personal attributes of teachers, including teaching aptitude, intrinsic motivation, and emotional intelligence, is equally vital, as these factors significantly affect their aptitude. This study aims to investigate the relationship between teaching aptitude and the performance of pupil-teachers, focusing on their D.El.Ed. take away and their level of achievement in Central Teacher Eligibility Test(CTET) which is a pre requisite for teaching upto class X in

India. The word Teaching Aptitude covers a wide range of attributes which determine an individual's innate ability or suitability for the role of Teacher.

Teaching is an art, based on the foundations of science, which expects teachers to acquire certain competencies to possess specific knowledge, master pedagogical skills and develop certain abilities to become fruitful in this profession. Teaching aptitude refers to the qualities, traits and skills of teaching, which a person possesses naturally or acquires through self-effort and which get reflected in his inclination towards teaching and are helpful to him in performing his job dexterously.

Teaching aptitude may refer to a person's ability or hypothetical potential for acquiring certain characteristics, mental abilities and inclination involved towards the teaching profession concerning which the individual has had little or no previous training.

Teaching aptitude, which is a combination of characteristics indicative of a teacher's capacity to acquire some specific skills and abilities of instruction, is an important aspect of deciding the special ability of a teacher. Precisely, one has an aptitude for teaching, if he/she has a favourable attitude towards the teaching profession, enjoys teaching, is interested in pedagogical matters and shows inclination towards teaching issues, prefers teaching to other alluring jobs, has a love for children, is witty and humorous, can lend an ear to the students, is unerringly patient, sympathetic, has an interest in the problems of the community and is responsive to the demands of the situation.

Aptitude embraces any characteristic which predisposes learning including intelligence, achievement, personality, interest and special skills. "In its original, broad definition aptitude means aptness, inclination, tendency, propensity, predisposition, fitness, or suitability for performance in some situation, usually involving formal or informal learning. Its meaning is akin to the concepts of susceptibility (to treatment or persuasion) and proneness (as in accident proneness). This definition admits motivational, volitional, affective, social and psychomotor, as well as cognitive, characteristics of learners as part of the concept of aptitude (although I deal only with the cognitive here). It also carries the strong implication of readiness for some particular learning situation and the mutual person/ situation compatibility in this condition. The notion of cultural compatibility of the first examples of teaching adaptation above fits this view of aptitude nicely."

The potential ease of learning particular skills or knowledge, Aptitudes are inferred through the observation of an individual's current skills or knowledge, generally through ability tests.

According to Prof. Fyn Como "Teaching aptitude is a complex capability; it includes such assets as "alertness", "witness", a propensity to check sudden understanding continuously in a variety of ways and hesitant attitude about using any one approach with all students". Teaching Aptitude is an ability to acquire proficiency or skill, with proper training. Teaching aptitude is necessary for teachers to do their pious job, in a meaningful manner.

Teachers with teaching aptitude tend to be more sensitive towards the needs and aspirations of their students, which further enables them to pace their teaching activities as per the interests and potentialities of their pupils. To fail in this respect is to invite boredom and possible failure, which in turn mitigates against proper performance. An imaginative, creative and innovative teacher may create inspiring situations, which grip the imagination, the emotions and the intellectual capacity to the degree that the pupil can solve his problems (educational as well as personal) himself, with some satisfaction to himself, and to the teacher

Teachers who commit to their profession can bring out the hidden potentialities of their students by adopting their self-confidence, teaching them methods of improvement and change and diligence etc. They can keep a balance between discipline and love. With a good sense of humour and the ability to think like their students, they can capture their students' attention. On the other hand, a disinterested lazy, short-tempered teacher is likely to mar things. He/she may not be able to create a conducive learning environment and infuse the feeling of safety among his students, which are the essential prerequisites for a successful teaching profession.

Academic and school performance

The complexity of academic performance starts from its conceptualization. Sometimes it is known as school readiness, academic achievement and school performance, but generally, the difference in concepts is only explained by semantics as they are used as synonyms. Conventionally, it has been agreed that academic performance should be used in university populations and school performance in regular and alternative basic education populations. We will point out just a few because there is a diversity of definitions. Several authors agree that academic performance is the result of learning, prompted by the teaching activity by the teacher and produced by the student. From a humanistic approach, Martinez (2007) states that academic performance is "the product given by the students and it is usually expressed through school grades" (p. 34). Fifteen years ago, Pizarro (1985) referred to academic performance as a measure of the indicative and responsive abilities that express, in an estimated way, what a person has learned as a result of a process of education or training For Caballero et al. (2007), academic performance involves meeting goals, achievements and objectives set in the program or course that a student attends. These are expressed through grades which are the result of an assessment that involves passing or not certain tests, subjects or courses. On their part, Torres and Rodriguez (2006 quoted by Willcox, 2011) define academic performance as the level of knowledge shown in an area or subject compared to the norm, and it is generally measured using the grade point average.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Leandro and Pelechano (2004) studied the wisdom and achievement motivation factors that have a correlation with academic performance and the motivational factors are more relevant to academic qualification than contemporary wisdom. Academic achievement is accomplished by the actual execution of class work in the school setting. Moreover (Johnson 1996,) 2004, Skaalvik and Skaalvik, (2004), Skaalvik and Skaalvik,(2006), and Sandra, (2002) revealed significant a relationship between academic performance and motivation.

Goel (2008) carried out a study on the teaching aptitude of preservice and in-service teachers. The major findings were: there was no significant difference found in the mean achievement scores of the pre-service teachers with respect to their streams of study, teaching experience, gender and marital status. The mean achievement score of the in-service teachers on teaching aptitude had been found significantly higher than that of the pre-service teachers.

Ranganathan (2008) studied the self-esteem and teaching aptitude of diplomas in teacher education students (DTED). The study revealed that there was a significant positive relationship between high self-esteem and teaching aptitude. There was no significant difference between gender and level of self-esteem and teaching aptitude among the students.

Jose Augustine (2010) studied teaching aptitude, competency, academic background and achievement in Educational Psychology. A sample of 200 student teachers from 5 colleges of teacher education in the Kottayam Revenue district in Kerala was taken for the study. Teaching

aptitude scale (TAS) structured and validated by M/s. Psycom Services was used for the study. The findings of the study were: There was a significant relationship between teaching competency and teaching aptitude of student teachers. There was no consistent positive relationship between academic background and the teaching of student teachers. There was no significant difference between men and women student teachers in teaching competency and teaching aptitude.

Sajan K. S. (2010) conducted a study on the teaching aptitude of student teachers and their academic achievements at the graduate level. He used the Teaching aptitude battery (TATB) by Singh and Sharma (1998). Major findings were that a dimension-wise teaching aptitude revealed that the highest scoring dimension was the professional information (75.81%) and the least scoring one was the professional interest (50.21%). Also, the female student teachers were found to score significantly high on teaching aptitude compared to their male counterparts. They also concluded that there existed no substantial correlation between marks obtained at the graduate level and scores obtained on teaching aptitude of student teachers.

Salman Kuraisy and Jarrar Ahmed (2010) studied the teaching aptitude of prospective teachers in relation to their academic background. The major findings of the study were: It was observed that the high academic group was significantly different from the low academic background group on mental ability, attitude towards children, interest in the profession and total teaching aptitude. The male subjects were found to be having a higher level of teaching aptitude as well as mental ability and professional information.

Fatima, Kaneez; Humera, Syeda (2011) have done research aimed to study the aptitude of B.Ed. trainee teachers towards teaching and academic achievement. The study was conducted at Aurangabad on a sample of 143 trainee teachers. The Teaching Aptitude Test Battery by Dr. R.P. Singh and Dr. S.N. Sharma was used to study teaching aptitude and academic achievement was obtained from the college records. They concluded that B.Ed. trainees have above-average level teaching aptitude & high academic achievement. The coefficient of the correlation between teaching aptitude and academic achievement is positive and low. There is no significant difference between male and female B.Ed. trainees for both variables.

Gurmit Singh (2011) conducted a study on the Job Satisfaction of Teacher Educators in Relation to their aptitude towards teaching. The major findings of the study were there was a positive and significant relationship between job satisfaction and aptitude towards teaching among teachers. There was a positive and significant relationship between job satisfaction and aptitude towards teaching among male teachers.

The Teaching Aptitude Test Battery developed by Singh and Sharma (2011) was administered and teaching aptitude was found to be average, even though students scored significantly low on mental ability and adaptability components of the test. On correlating percentage in boards, on the basis of which students are granted admission in the institute, with teaching aptitude as well as with mental ability, a positive but weak correlation was found in both cases. No significant correlation was found between previous educational qualifications and teaching aptitude, as well as between age and teaching aptitude, although adaptability positively and significantly correlated with age.

Utpal Kalita (2016) conducted a study to assess the aptitude of high school teachers towards teaching in relation to some demographic variables i.e. gender and educational level. For that, the Teaching Aptitude Test Battery (TATB) developed by Shamim Karim and Ashok Kumar Dixit is administered to a sample of 120 teachers of 12 provincialized high schools of Kamrup

District of Assam. The findings were: Except for optimistic attitudes, the mean score of teaching aptitude of high school teachers in all categories was very high. There was no significant difference in teaching aptitude of the male and female teachers of high school. There was no significant difference in teaching aptitude of the graduate and post-graduate teachers of high school.

METHODOLOGY

This study aims to identify the correlation of Teaching Aptitude in respect to achievement of D.El.Ed. trainees in Central Teacher Eligibility Test. For conducting this study Descriptive survey method was used. Sample size of 122 trainees of D.El.Ed. was taken into account. Teaching Aptitude scale was used to gather academic records of class 10th, 12th D.El.Ed. and CTET Scores.

Standard Deviation, Mean, Percentage Analysis, T-Test were utilised to analyse the divergence between Pre & Post test scores regarding Teaching Aptitude Pearson product Moment Correlation: was used to find the relationship between Teaching Aptitude and performance.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

A Study of Teaching Aptitude on D.El.Ed. Performance and CTET Success: A Correlation Analysis

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the relationship between the teaching aptitude of pupil-teachers and their performance in the CTET.
2. To examine the correlation between the performance of pupil-teachers in the D.El.Ed. program and their CTET performance.
3. To identify if there are significant mean differences in the teaching aptitude of pupil-teachers from different academic backgrounds (Arts, Commerce, Science).

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

1. There is no significant relationship between the teaching aptitude of pupil-teachers and their performance in the Central Teacher Eligibility Test (CTET).
2. There is no significant relationship between the performance of pupil-teachers in the Diploma in Elementary Education (D.El.Ed.) program and their performance in the CTET.
3. There is no significant mean difference in the teaching aptitude of pupil-teachers from Arts, Commerce, and Science backgrounds

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Objective 1: Relationship between Teaching Aptitude and CTET Performance

Variable	N	'r' value
Teaching Aptitude	65	0.049
CTET Performance	65	
Df (63)	0.25 at 0.05 level of significance	

In the above table the analysis revealed a Pearson correlation coefficient (r) of 0.049 between the teaching aptitude of pupil-teachers and their performance in the Central Teacher Eligibility Test (CTET), which was statistically insignificant at the 0.05 level. This finding suggests that there is no significant relationship between teaching aptitude and CTET performance among the sampled pupil-teachers.

Objective 2: Relationship between D.El.Ed. Performance and CTET Performance

Variable	N	'r' value
D.El.Ed. performance	122	0.329
CTET Performance	122	
Df (63)	0.194 at 0.05 level of significance	

In the above table the analysis indicates a Pearson correlation coefficient (r) of 0.329 between pupil-teachers' performance in the Diploma in Elementary Education (D.El.Ed.) program and their Central Teacher Eligibility Test (CTET) scores, which is statistically significant at the 0.05 level. This finding suggests a moderate positive correlation, implying that higher academic achievement in the D.El.Ed. program is associated with better performance in the CTET.

Objective 3: Differences in Teaching Aptitude Across Different Academic Backgrounds

Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Between Groups	85.996	2	42.998	1.346	0.264
Within Group	3802.684	119	31.955		
Total	3888.681	121			

In the above table the analysis you described indicates that the teaching aptitude of pupil-teachers from Arts, Commerce, and Science backgrounds does not differ significantly that yielded an F-value of 1.346, which is below the critical F-value of 3.01, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. Subsequent post-hoc t-tests also showed no significant differences between the groups.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

The study's findings indicate a moderate correlation between pupil-teachers' performance in the D.El.Ed. program and their CTET results, suggesting that academic achievement during teacher training moderately predicts success in certification exams. However, teaching aptitude alone does not significantly impact CTET success. This suggests that while teaching aptitude is crucial for effective teaching, it may not directly translate to higher scores in standardized exams like the CTET. Studies have not identified any constructive correlation between teaching aptitude and academic achievement.

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS

Analysis of the research reflects the importance of Teaching Aptitude and Academic achievements in designing the Academic career of D.El.Ed. students. These outcomes go a longways in framing of policies regarding Education.

Evaluating Aptitude: To ascertain the suitability of an individual for discharge of teaching related responsibilities. Specific assessments evaluate the qualities that are essential for this profession.

Designing Curriculum : Curriculum needs to assimilate the programme needs and also correlate them with first hand experiences of Trainees.

Planned Interventions : Planning interventions to meet the requirements and fill the gaps in professional competencies.

CONCLUSION

An individual's level of achievement in D.El.Ed. course is majority determined by the combination of Teaching Aptitude & their Academic background. Though the scope of Teacher Training is much wider & these attributes are just a part of it. The readiness of a trainee to become teacher is dependant on a set of other attributes which involve Academic background internal motivation, inter and intrapersonal relationship etc.

Overall, it is important to consider a range of factors when assessing the effectiveness of teaching and teacher training programs, including the individual's aptitude, training, and experience, as well as the specific needs of the students and the broader educational context

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